

Electrometric Studies on the Precipitation of Hydrrous Oxides of Some Quadrivalent Cations. Part I. Precipitation of Zirconium Hydroxide from Solutions of Zirconium Salts

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The precipitation of basic salts and hydroxide of zirconium from solutions of its sulphate, oxychloride, and nitrate has been studied. Conductometric and *pH* titrations of the salt solutions with sodium hydroxide show that the precipitated hydroxide contains appreciable quantities of the anions. Compositions of the basic salts, thus obtained, have been deduced from the titration curves. Hydrolysis of these salts have been found to be a slow process. The increasing order of anion penetration is the same as the co-ordinating power of the respective anions, viz., nitrate, chloride, and sulphate.

Titrations of zirconium sulphate solutions against baryta show that the initially precipitated basic sulphate gives up the anion gradually with little change in the *pH* or the conductance and the ultimate product consists of almost pure hydroxide.

The mechanism of precipitation of the hydroxides of quadrivalent cations (Zr^{4+} , Hf^{4+} , Th^{4+}) by alkalis has been little studied. Evidence for the formation of zirconates (Hildebrand, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 35, 847) as well as its contradiction (Britton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2120) is found in literature. Chauvenet (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1920, ix, 13, 82) titrated zirconium sulphate solutions conductometrically and from the titration curves he inferred the formation of basic sulphates of the formulas $ZrOSO_4$ and $ZrOSO_4 \cdot ZrO_2$. Britton (*loc. cit.*) could not confirm these contentions from *pH* titrations. Adolf and Pauli (*Kolloid Z.*, 1921, 29, 172) found that hydrolysis of solutions of zirconium oxychloride of concentrations between 0.0022*M* and 0.125*M* varied irregularly on standing. Britton (*loc. cit.*), on the basis of potentiometric titrations of different zirconium salt solutions, suggested the presence of an equilibrium mixture of a basic salt and free acid in aqueous solutions of these salts. On addition of alkali, the free acid is supposed to be neutralised with the consequent precipitation of the basic salt. No work appears to have been done on zirconium nitrate on these lines. In view of the difference of opinion regarding the composition of the basic salts, it was considered worthwhile to reinvestigate these equilibria.

EXPERIMENTAL

Procedure

A freshly prepared solution of the zirconium salt (10 c.c.) was taken in a vessel (kept in a thermostat at 25°) in which a current of nitrogen was passed during titration. Sodium hydroxide or baryta solution was added from a microburette and conductance or *pH* readings were taken after each addition of alkali.

Subsequently 10 c.c. of the solution was taken in each of several pyrex bottles. The air in the bottles was displaced by nitrogen and increasing quantities of the standard alkali were added to each of them. The bottles were shaken from time to time and conduc-

tance and *pH* readings of the mixtures were taken in each case after an interval of 3 days. On keeping the bottles for a longer period, the conductance and *pH* readings remained unchanged, showing attainment of equilibrium during this period. These will henceforth be referred to as equilibrium (bottle) titrations.

For measurements of *pH*, a Beckman *pH* meter (model H-2) was used; for measurements of conductance, a conductivity bridge (Serfass, model RCM 15) was used.

Zirconium Sulphate

The composition of L.R., B. D. H. sample of zirconium sulphate used was determined by analysis as $Zr(SO_4)_2 \cdot 0.025H_2SO_4 \cdot 3.9 H_2O$. This sample of zirconium sulphate (0.401 g.) was dissolved in water and 1.0299 *N*- H_2SO_4 (5 c.c.) was added to it to prevent hydrolysis. The volume was made to 250 c.c. A 0.176*N*-solution of carbonate-free NaOH and a 0.175*N* solution of baryta were used for the titrations.

Precipitation with NaOH.—The results of continued and equilibrium *pH* titrations against 0.176*N*-NaOH at 25° are recorded in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1

×—Contd. titration.
●—Bottle "

FIG. 2

●—Contd. titration.
×—Bottle "

The volume of NaOH needed for neutralisation of free H_2SO_4 in 10 c.c. of the zirconium sulphate solution would be 1.17 c.c. Assuming that pure zirconium hydroxide is precipitated afterwards, the amount of sodium hydroxide required for this purpose would be 1.03 c.c. Total volume of alkali needed should then be 2.2 c.c.

The neutralisation curve shows that in the continued titration there is at first a flat portion showing the gradual neutralisation of free sulphuric acid. This is followed by a steep rise, the inflection occurring when 2.01 c.c. of alkali had been added. At this stage, the calculated composition of the precipitate was $ZrO_2 \cdot 0.36SO_3$. Britton (*loc. cit.*) had

reported that this inflection occurred when three equivalents of alkali had been added. Further addition of alkali was reported to cause partial decomposition of the precipitate even beyond the stage when the composition of the precipitate corresponded with the formula $ZrO_2 \cdot 0.16SO_3$.

Our results of equilibrium titration show that hydrolysis of zirconium sulphate is a slow reaction. The inflection occurs at 2.13 c.c. and the calculated composition of the precipitate corresponds to the formula $ZrO_2 \cdot 0.14SO_3$. The remaining acid was not extracted from the basic salt even by contact with the alkali for more than 72 hours.

The results of conductometric titrations of zirconium sulphate against sodium hydroxide are shown in Fig. 2. In the continued and in equilibrium titrations, the first breaks occurred when 0.8 c.c. of alkali had been added. The solution became opalescent and precipitation began at this stage. This was followed by a regular fall in conductance and then a rounded portion corresponding to the attack of the basic salt by the alkali. The rounded portion was followed by a straight line denoting a sharp rise in conductance produced by the free alkali. The end points obtained by drawing tangents to the curves show that the volumes of the alkali consumed in the continued and equilibrium titrations are 2.03 c.c. and 2.13 c.c. respectively, thus corroborating the results obtained by pH titrations.

Precipitation with Barium Hydroxide.—Use of barium hydroxide is more advantageous in the study of metallic sulphates because it not only neutralises the acid obtained by hydrolysis, but also precipitates an equivalent amount of barium sulphate, thus producing sharper breaks in the conductivity curves (Harned, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **39**, 254).

Ba(OH)₂ (c.c.).

FIG. 3

●—Contd. titration.

X—Bottle "

Ba(OH)₂ (c.c.).

FIG. 4

●—Contd. titration.

X—Bottle "

Our results of pH titrations with baryta (Fig. 3) show that more of alkali is consumed both in continued as well as equilibrium titrations (2.13 c.c. and 2.2 c.c. respectively). It is interesting to note that in equilibrium titrations, the amount of alkali consumed corresponds to what would be required for the precipitation of pure zirconium hydroxide,

a fact which has been further confirmed by conductometric titrations (Fig. 4), the latter showing some interesting features. The general appearance of the curves of continued and equilibrium titrations being similar, only the latter will be discussed. The initial decrease in conductance corresponds to neutralisation of free sulphuric acid. Beginning of precipitation of zirconium hydroxide is marked by a break which is not very pronounced. After this, the curve becomes more steep, probably because not only the acid is neutralised by the alkali, but zirconium ions are also precipitated. When 2.0 c.c. of alkali had been added, conductance became practically zero, indicating that practically all ions had been removed from the solution, or in other words, precipitation of zirconium and sulphate ions was complete. The conductance did not rise during the addition of the next 0.2 c.c. of barium hydroxide, indicating that this much of baryta was taken up by the precipitate in some way. As the precipitate consisted of basic zirconium sulphate, addition of baryta must be responsible for its conversion into zirconium hydroxide, barium sulphate being formed simultaneously. All these products being insoluble, conductance does not rise during this stage.

The above results can also be explained satisfactorily by the application of phase rule to the system. Addition of barium hydroxide in the initial stages causes precipitation of the basic sulphate according to the equation:

While the precipitation of the basic sulphate proceeds, there are four phases in the system, viz., water vapour, solution, basic zirconium sulphate, and barium sulphate. Under these conditions, the number of components is four, one of which is water, the remaining being any three of the four independent species shown in the above equation. According to the phase rule, the system can then possess two degrees of freedom. These apparently are temperature and pressure. But on addition of a slight excess of baryta beyond the stage, when precipitation of zirconium as basic sulphate is complete, a new phase, *i.e.*, pure zirconium hydroxide, makes its appearance. The number of degrees of freedom is thereby reduced to unity. The temperature of the system during these titrations having been maintained constant, the only degree of freedom is lost and the system becomes non-variant as shown by the flat portions in the titration curves which show the constancy of the property (conductance) of the system. The results of *pH* titrations in this region are similar to those of conductometric titrations, as shown by curves in Fig. 5 which depict the results of titrations in which 25 c.c. of the same zirconium sulphate solution was used instead of 10 c.c. as in other titrations.

Zirconium Oxychloride

0.02*M* Aqueous solutions of Merck's G. R. zirconium oxychloride were titrated against 0.3875*N*-NaOH. The solutions were clear but acidic owing to hydrolysis. The first portion of the continued *pH* titration curve (Fig. 6) shows that the free acid is gradually neutralised by alkali, leaving basic zirconium chloride. The inflection occurs when 0.96 c.c. of alkali has been added. The composition of the basic salt therefore corresponds to the formula $\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_{3.86}\text{Cl}_{0.14}$. Britton's titration curve (*loc. cit.*) was also similar though he obtained a much less basic precipitate $\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_{3.5}\text{Cl}_{0.5}$. That these are not equilibrium values is shown by the equilibrium titration curve shown in the same figure. In this case, the inflection occurred when 0.99 c.c. of alkali had been added, the composition of the precipitate corresponding to the formula, $\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_{3.92}\text{Cl}_{0.08}$. This shows that even

an interval of five minutes, allowed after addition of each portion of alkali in our continued titrations, was not enough though nearly so to bring about an equilibrium.

FIG. 5. Titrations of $Zr(SO_4)_2$.

Conductometric titration curves of zirconium oxychloride (Fig. 6.) against NaOH show that conductance initially falls due to the neutralisation of highly conducting hydrogen ions. Commencement of precipitation is shown by breaks in the curves in both continued and equilibrium titrations when about 0.4 c.c. of alkali has been added. The straight curves are followed by curved portions in both cases, resulting from the attack of the precipitate by the alkali. The next portion of the curve in both cases is a straight line denoting sharp rise in conductance produced by the free alkali. The amounts of alkali needed for complete precipitation in both cases, as determined by extrapolation from the curves, were practically the same as deduced from the corresponding pH titration curves.

Zirconium Nitrate

0.01M Aqueous solutions of zirconium nitrate (L. R., B.D.H) and 0.339N carbonate-free sodium hydroxide were used in the investigations. The purity of the sample of zirconium nitrate was checked gravimetrically.

Continued pH-metric and conductometric titrations show that the composition of the basic salt precipitated is $Zr(OH)_{3.87}(NO_3)_{0.13}$. The general appearance of the curves (Fig. 7) is similar to those in the equilibrium titration curves. These were also plotted as in the case of the oxychloride. The curves show that after three days, a more basic precipitate having the composition $Zr(OH)_{3.94}(NO_3)_{0.06}$ is formed.

Comparison of the results of titrations of solutions of zirconium sulphate, oxychloride and nitrate shows that the basic salts of the formulas $Zr(OH)_{3.72}(SO_4)_{0.14}$, $Zr(OH)_{3.95}Cl_{0.05}$, and $Zr(OH)_{3.94}(NO_3)_{0.06}$ are obtained at equilibrium with excess of sodium hy-

FIG. 6. Titrations with $ZrOCl_2$.
1, 4 : Contd. titrations.
2, 3 : Bottle ,,

FIG. 7. Titrations with $Zr(NO_3)_4$.
x—Contd. titrations.
o—Bottle ,,

dioxide. Thus anion penetration is greatest in the case of sulphate and is the least in the case of nitrate. This is in conformity with the fact that the order of co-ordinating power of these ions is also the same (Bailar, "The Chemistry of Co-ordination Compounds", Reinhold Publishing Corporation, 1956, p.446).